

CULTURAL AND PRAGMATIC FEATURES OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN MODERN LINGUISTICS

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ABSTRACT The article deals with the basic features have representational meaning which means they contribute conceptual information and the propositional meaning. Specifically, they represent information which signals more or less specifically the force of the direct basic message of the sentence.

Keywords: pragmatic markers, basic message, sentence, feature, signal, expression.

INTRODUCTION

Messages, and hence their associated pragmatic markers, fall into four types. First, there is a single, basic message, which uses the sentence proposition as its message content. Basic markers, which signal more or less specifically the force (the kind of message in contrast to its content) of the basic message, include sentence mood and lexical expressions. These markers are illustrated by the examples in (1), with the pragmatic feature in boldface type [3, 102].

a) I regret that he is still here.

b) Admittedly, I was taken in.

c) The cat is very sick.

Sentence (1a) is an expression of regret, and sentence (1b) an admission. Sentence (1c) has no lexical basic feature, as do the first two, but its declarative mood signals that it is the expression of belief (a claim, a report) that the state of the world expressed by the propositional content is true.

Second, there are commentary messages, which provide a comment on the basic message. Commentary messages, and hence the presence of commentary markers, are optional - a sentence need not contain any. When they do occur,

their message is typically very general, with a single word often signaling both the message force and content. Obviously, they constitute pragmatic idioms. The sentences in (2) illustrate this type of feature.

(2) a) *Stupidly, Sara didn't fax the correct form in on time.*

b) *Frankly, we should be there by now*

In (2a), for example, the basic message is (arguably) a report while the commentary message, signaled by stupidly, is that the speaker believes Sara's failure to act to have been stupid. In (2b), the frankly signals that the basic message which follows is, in the speaker's opinion, not going to be well received by the addressee.

Third, there are parallel messages, also optional, which signal an entire message separate from the basic and any commentary messages. The sentences in (3) are illustrative of parallel features.

(3) a) *John, you are very noisy.*

b) *In God's name, what are you doing now?*

In (3a), for example. the speaker, in addition to the basic message of a claim that John is being very noisy, is conveying a message, signaled by John, that it is John who is being addressed. while in (3b), the in God's name signals exasperation on the part of the speaker.

Finally, there are discourse messages, again optional, which signal a message specifying how the basic message is related to the foregoing discourse. The sentences in (4) illustrate these features.

(4) a) *Jacob was very tired. So, he left early.*

b) *Martha's party is tomorrow. Incidentally, when is your party?*

Here, in (4a), the so signals that the report that he left early is a conclusion based on the message conveyed by the preceding sentence, while in (4b), the incidentally signals that the following basic message is going to reflect a shift in topic.

To summarize to this point, a basic marker signals the force of the

basic message, a commentary feature signals a message which comments on the basic message, a parallel feature signals a message in addition to the basic message, and a discourse marker signals the relationship of the basic message to the foregoing discourse. Although it is rare to find four types of pragmatic features in a single sentence, it does occur, as in (5) [2, 303].

(5) *I appreciate that you are a member of the Police Benevolent Association and a supporter of the baseball league. However, quite frankly Sir, I estimate that you were going a bit more than 86 miles per hour.*

Before looking at these four types of markers in detail, I want to make a few general remarks. First, to reiterate a point made above, pragmatic markers are not part of the propositional content of the sentence. They are separate and distinct. It follows from this that for a given lexical expression (e.g., truthfully, amazingly) in a particular sentence, there is no overlapping of functions. When an expression functions as one type of pragmatic marker, it does not function as a part of the propositional content; and vice versa. In addition, when an expression is functioning as one type of pragmatic marker, it cannot at the same time function as a second type. In some cases when there are homophonous expressions, for example, truthfully, the expression cannot occur in the same frame, so there is no question of ambiguity. For example, in (6a),

(6) a) *Truthfully, you should have answered.*

b) *You should have answered truthfully.*

c) *Truthfully, you should have answered truthfully.*

The speaker signals that the manner of speaking is truthful, not disingenuous, whereas in (6b), the truthfully is part of the proposition and modifies the manner of answering. The interpretation of the expressions cannot be interchanged. In fact, (6c) shows that the two meanings can co-exist with no problem. However, there are a few cases like "Now where are we?" where there is an ambiguity. Is it the adverbial now, with a time interpretation; or is it the

discourse marker now, with a focusing function? When there is a comma intonation present, it is always the latter.

Second, pragmatic markers carry meaning. But whereas basic, commentary, and parallel markers, like the sentence proposition, have representational meaning, in virtue of which they denote concepts, the discourse markers have procedural meaning and specify how the sentence of which they are a part is related to the preceding discourse. I will address these points as we go along [1, 22].

Third, pragmatic markers signal messages that apply only to the direct basic message. They do not apply to any indirect messages which may be implicated by the direct basic message. For example, the indirect interpretation of (7a)

(7) a) Unfortunately, I am cold.

b) Confidentially, would you like a drink?

c) Candidly, he is married to his work. (He is dedicated to his work.)

d) I suspect his mind rusted on vacation. (I suspect he got a little out of practice.)

As a request to turn up the heat is unaffected by the commentary marker *unfortunately*. Similarly, the indirect message in (7b), that the speaker is asking if the addressee will stay and talk with him after being brought the drink, is unaffected by the marker *confidentially*. In (7c-d) where the direct message is taken to be figurative not literal, the pragmatic markers apply to the figurative, direct interpretations, but not to any indirect interpretations [4, 214].

Fourth, nearly all pragmatic markers may occur in sentence-initial position (*though* is one exception) and usually occur there. There are occasions when they will occur medially or finally, as in (8), but in these cases the marker is set off by a comma intonation to distinguish it from a homophonous form used as part of the proposition.

(8) a) John is, I admit, the best person by far for the job.

b) She was, confidentially, a bright scholar and a fantastic athlete.

c) Harry is going to go, however.

CONCLUSION

Summing up of all what has just been said we can conclude that pragmatic features are drawn from all segments of the grammar. Verbs, nouns, and adverbs as well as idioms such as *ok* are all pressed into service as pragmatic markers. But for the most part, the meaning of the expression, when used as a pragmatic marker, is the same as when it is used as a propositional formative and it is only its function which differs. In those cases where there is a difference, the lexical expression must be marked for the different meaning.

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